

DIALECTICAL CONTENT OF THE AXIOLOGICAL PERSONALITY PICTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses axiological influence to the personal spirituality, the justification of the socio-philosophical analysis of the axiological impact of art on personal spirituality as a pressing social problem, the clarification of the essence, structure and components of the axiological impact of art on personal spirituality, the systematization of the foundations of the socio-philosophical analysis of the axiological impact of art on personal spirituality, and the study of the priority tasks of the socio-philosophical analysis of the axiological impact of art on personal spirituality in the future.

Introduction

Art is not only a form of social consciousness but also possesses qualities that define it as a unique way of comprehending reality in an educational and enlightening sense. An artistic image is a distinct form of assimilating and expressing reality, through which humanity concretizes its individual and social consciousness within historical and cultural experience via artistic and creative activity. The artistic image represents a mode of thinking within art and reflects its essence; thus, it recreates life in a concrete, emotional, and general manner from an educational perspective. An artistic image embodies both the cultural and intellectual energy of its creator, while its personal character reflects one of the most important features of art. Therefore, in defining the characteristics of art as a medium for expressing spirituality, it is essential to substantiate the artistic image as a unique educational phenomenon.

Consequently, the cultivation of spirituality plays a vital role in equipping creators with educational and ideological qualities within culture and art. From this perspective:

- First, every society should implement measures and create conditions aimed at developing the moral and spiritual image of its creators at a high level.
- Second, during processes of cultural transformation, it is necessary to study and analyze national cultural foundations deeply, preserving national elements and integrating them into public consciousness.
- Third, in culture and art, the manifestation of national elements as foundational indicates the identity and existence of a nation, which should be taught systematically to practitioners in the field.

Literature review and methods

In Uzbekistan, the axiological influence of art on personal spirituality has been explored from philosophical, socio-anthropological, and psychological perspectives by M. Kakhharova, A. Mavrulov, J. Tulenov, G. Tulenova, E. Yusupov, and O. G'aybullaev. Psychological aspects of the problem have been studied by M. Davletshin, V. Karimova, A. Leontiev, A. Maslow, Z. Nishonova, L. Rubinshteyn, N. Safaev, and E. G'oziev.

In the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, fundamental research on the axiological influence of art on personal spirituality has been conducted and continues today. Scholars who have studied moral education include A. Frolov, V. Kinelev, I. Kosova, B. Azarov, L. Vygotsky, S. Rubinshteyn, V. Bespalko, and A. Kovalyov.

In Western countries, researchers such as James R. Ozinga, Jakob Neusner, George Herbert Palmer, Robin Gill, Andrew Michael Flescher, and Daniel L. Vorthen have explored the theoretical foundations of moral education.

However, research on the role and significance of axiological influence in the formation of personal spirituality, particularly its dialectical content, remains scarce.

Results And Discussion

Emotions occupy a crucial place in art. Art serves as a means of communication essential for humanity's movement toward goodness, connecting these interactions with particular emotions. However, art does not reflect human emotions and thoughts abstractly but through vivid artistic images. In essence, without emotions, one cannot reach the core of life, including the fundamental meaning of art, either in the past or the future.

Emotions in art possess a distinct quality compared to scientific fields. While emotions may guide research in science and technology, they are not directly visible in scientific results. Art, however, is a treasury of unique emotions and experiences.

In art, emotions form the material foundation for creating artistic images. Artistic emotions differ from ordinary, everyday feelings as well as from scientific emotions. They are a product of generalization, encompassing not the experience of a single individual or group, but the accumulated socio-historical experience of ancestors. According to psychologists, ordinary life emotions are socialized through art and acquire the status of reasoned feelings.

Artistic emotions demand active and serious reflection from creators. The product of creation does not merely express the artist's momentary feelings but reflects their consistent thoughts and experiences about life. Even in poetry, the art form closest to the inner world, an artist cannot be limited to simply expressing transient emotions. The works of great poets such as Nizami, Sa'di, Bedil, Mirza Ghalib, Jami, Navoi, Mashrab, Muqimi, and Furqat retain independent artistic value while also possessing generalizing qualities. Poetry consistently evokes profound emotions in the hearts of people.

Art is polished through the interplay of artistic emotions and logical reasoning. For instance, in Shayxzoda's play *"Mirzo Ulug'bek"*, the philosophical debates between the great scholar and Bobo Kayfiy have an unparalleled impact on the audience's emotions. On stage, in films, and through specific artistic images, political passions, scientific inquiries, psychological experiences, crises of belief, and conflicting confrontations are manifested in logical form. In an artistic image, both thoughts and emotions are represented, with emotion often reinforcing

the idea. When the richness of thought and the intensity of emotion harmoniously combine in art, the work's artistic and philosophical value increases.

In art, reality is reflected in the unity of both particular and general aspects. This connection links artistic images to life events, drawing art closer to philosophy. Observing life broadly and expressing it in conjunction with its "substance and soul" demonstrates the powerful and enduring beauty of art. The "singularity" of art differs significantly from the "oneness" of life. The uniqueness of an artistic image is the result of a deliberate choice: a true artist selects the most essential life factors. The artist's talent lies in skillfully choosing these elements.

The ability to concisely express a social idea through an artistic image is an integral component of artistic talent. Conciseness depends on artistic taste, the artist's personality, and the stylistic orientation of the work. For this reason, the works of A. Qodiriy, Oybek, P. Qodirov, O. Yoqubov, Sh. Xolmirzaev, O. Hoshimov, and Tog'ay Murod each differ from one another.

The unity of the particular and the general is essential for creating a mature artistic image. In art, this is achieved through categorization, which serves as a method of generalizing the important aspects of life based on aesthetic emotions and represents one of the fundamental laws of artistic creation. The method of artistic generalization—categorization, or typification—is connected to life models. Life models are the most vivid, conspicuous, and openly or subtly occurring human behaviors and social factors. In art, depicting life models, i.e., categorizing them, occurs simultaneously with creating unique artistic images. Individualization is an inseparable part of categorization. Singularization strengthens the credibility of life models, reflecting historical content specific to a particular era.

An artist's task is not merely to find ready-made symbols or models and mechanically depict them in literature or on screen. The artist expresses the essential characteristics of their era through their images, psychological states, actions, and behavior. Even when using a pre-existing symbol, the artist proceeds via selection and generalization, experiencing a complex creative process. In this process, the artist mobilizes all their thoughts, emotions, memories, life experience, reasoning, and worldview.

Art is not a literal reproduction of life. Even when an artist finds a striking social model, they may abandon it if necessary. Directly transferring an event from life into an artwork destroys its authenticity and prevents it from becoming an artistic truth. The social model in life, when represented in art, is generalized through categorization (typification), which serves as a method of artistic generalization.

The primary method of categorization (typification) in art is the study and comparison of numerous events. In art, an artistic image selects the most significant aspects of life models and unifies them within a single character. Based on this principle, the characters Otabek, Anvar, Ra'no, Ulug'bek, Navoi, and Babur were created. The protagonists of Abdulla Qodiriy's novels "*O'tkan kunlar*" and "*Mehrobdan chayon*" each possess a distinct inner world, identity, facial features, gestures, manner of speaking, and behavior. Similarly, the characters Yusufbek Hoji, O'zbekoyim, Otabek, Kumush, Zaynab, Mirzakarim Qutidor, Oftob Oyim, Hasanali, Homid,

Anvar, Ra'no, Khudoyorkhon, and Abdurahmon Domla each represent a unique universe, leaving a lasting imprint on the reader's mind and heart.

Generalization and categorization (typification) are realized through artistic means. The art of expression is an extremely complex phenomenon, accessible only to those with extraordinary talent. This is why the works of genius creators such as Jami, Sa'di, Nizami, Navoi, Babur, Mashrab, Bedil, and Behzod have endured for centuries due to their artistic power. In generalization and categorization (typification), expressive tools such as exaggeration and vivification play a crucial role. Exaggeration is a necessary condition for categorization and is especially characteristic of satirical forms (including hyperbole and absurdity). Exaggeration serves to reveal hidden, inconspicuous, or overlooked aspects of life.

Art extensively employs various forms of exaggeration. Some of these are extraordinary, almost inconceivable expressions that magnify the internal and external layers of human behavior. In certain artistic images, exaggeration uncovers realities hidden behind mundane trivialities. In other forms of exaggeration, however, a semblance of life-like truth is preserved. Through such exaggeration, profound descriptions enable the depiction of the multi-faceted and authentic nature of artistic characters.

No single type of exaggeration can be considered absolute. The methods of categorization (typification) depend on the aesthetic and conceptual objectives, styles, and chosen art forms of the artist. Nevertheless, regardless of the path the artist chooses, they are inevitably compelled to use both exaggeration and vivification. Exaggeration and anthropomorphization serve to reveal the inner essence of events and to facilitate their aesthetic perception by the audience, reader, or listener. It should be noted that these two types of artistic generalization rarely appear in "pure" form. In practice, across artistic disciplines and creative activities, they are intertwined and manifested in a blended manner.

Art is alive through artistic truth. In aesthetics, artistic truth occupies a central position, encompassing the subject, duty, and questions of authenticity in art's relationship to reality. If the theory of knowledge concerns truth in cognition, artistic truth is the concept within aesthetics. While they share similarities, artistic truth and empirical reality are not identical. Artistic truth is the reality of life recreated through the means of art.

Bringing all unfiltered "trivialities" of reality into art leads to a crude distortion of truth. Artistic truth embodies the artist's personal imprint, worldview, life experiences, emotions, and thoughts. Aesthetic aspiration is the most essential marker of artistic truth.

Clarity and reliability are integral components of artistic truth. Even if we have not witnessed or directly experienced the events depicted in rare works of art, we do not doubt their veracity. For example, contemporary Uzbek readers have neither seen nor participated in the events portrayed in Abdulla Qodiriy's novels "*O'tkan kunlar*" and "*Mehrobdan chayon*", yet they trust them. This is because the artistic truth in these works is so powerful that the veracity of the life scenes and characters created through artistic means is unquestionable.

Clarity and reliability are not exclusive to literature; they are characteristic of all art forms. For instance, in the works of the fifteenth-century master painter Kamoliddin Behzod, life scenes, human characters, and depictions of birds and animals are rendered with exceptional precision and credibility. Through miniature painting (without shading), the artist elevates everyday life challenges and life truths to a high level of artistic expression.

Artistic truth always possesses two “wings”: it simultaneously requires resemblance to reality and distinction from it. Even in painting, the artist cannot limit the character of a depicted person merely to their likeness. In painting, creating resemblance is only the first step; it is followed by revealing the aesthetic and educational essence of the depicted person. This process demands the full intellectual and emotional mastery of the artist. The works of Uzbek masters of painting such as Kamoliddin Behzod, Abdulhaq Abdullaev, and Malik Nabiev exemplify the perfect harmony between external likeness and the expression of the inner world.

In art, artistic truth is never entirely merged with the object it represents. A work must simultaneously resemble and differ from its reference.

In art, conventionality is a multi-layered concept. It primarily signifies not reality itself but its representation through artistic means. A depiction is never identical to the object or event portrayed, and artistic truth is never exactly the same as life. Therefore, in art, things are always represented on the basis of convention.

In visual arts, painters use colors and lines, sculptors employ volume, writers utilize words, and composers work with sound—all based on artistic convention. In each art form, reality is expressed through specific means. In music, for instance, there is no visible world; in visual art or linear drawing (graphics), volume and richness of sound cannot be perceived. These characteristics arise on the basis of artistic convention.

Regardless of the tools an artist uses, it is never possible to fully reveal all aspects of an event. However, an artistic image attains richer meaning than the material objects or events on which it is based. By clearly highlighting the most important aspects, the artistic image achieves completeness. In this way, a reality perceived through convention gives rise to an artistic truth that is richer than the mere fact or object.

The conventionality inherent in the depiction of events in art differs from the special type of conventionality that constitutes artistic generalization. This type of conventionality serves to reveal the hidden or imperceptible aspects of events and human behavior. Such conventionality reflects the inner essence of reality and often necessitates departure from natural forms of events.

In practice, conventionality and life-likeness are never encountered separately. These two systems of artistic means are always interconnected to some degree, interacting with each other. In particular works or in the oeuvre of particular artists, one or the other system may be dominant.

Each art form possesses its own criteria for conventionality. Many shortcomings in adapting great literary works to film can often be explained by filmmakers’ inability to translate literary conventions into cinematic conventions. Transferring artistic generalizations from one art form to another without adjustment can lead to artistic dispersion, a loss of cohesion in the artistic image, and a deviation from artistic truth.

An artist’s keen insight and emotional capacity enable them, by synthesizing scattered observations and information, to recreate entire historical periods through unified images and artistic representations, or to discover phenomena that, though unseen in their own experience, exist in reality. The richer and more diverse an artist’s emotional and intellectual experience, the more effective and meaningful their insight. Familiarity with events and the

possession of rich impressions facilitate the practice of insight. Uncovering the “sudden” or “unexpected” truths of life with insight is, in essence, the ability to integrate latent information and experiences within the artist’s psyche and immediately apply them.

The content of an artistic image may change in the process of its creation, sometimes emerging after repeated reflection. Works by artists such as Navoiy, Bobur, Behzod, Mashrab, Muqimiy, Furqat, Qodiriy, Qahhor, Oybek, and Cho’lpon were produced under complex conditions through painstaking labor, and throughout the creative process, their perspectives on contemporaries, their era, and their characters evolved.

Characters who “step into” life from an artist’s imagination often begin to live independently of the creator’s will. For this reason, many artists note, sometimes with frustration, that their characters follow paths different from those intended, even acting autonomously.

An artist depicts a character’s behavior based on observations, employing various artistic means. The artist achieves success only when the character’s actions authentically reflect their envisioned realism and express their aspirations, intentions, and desires.

Conclusion

In conclusion, art reflects the essence of the social life of diverse peoples and nations, evolving and transforming alongside societal change. Accordingly, it represents a dialectical social-cultural and aesthetic-axiological phenomenon.

The artist strives for their thoughts, emotions, and experiences to become the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of others; for what they perceive to be perceived by others; for their intellectual property to be shared as collective knowledge. Ultimately, the artist transfers their creative plan into the artistic fabric of the work. With the creation of the work, the artistic process is completed, and the artistic image enters a new stage of life—the stage of aesthetic perception. At this point, the artistic image comes alive and begins to move. If it is not perceived, it remains a mere material object.

An artist often tailors a work for a specific reader or audience, which involves selecting events and choosing appropriate means of expression. In art, perception is the reflection of the content of literature, theater, cinema, or visual art in the mind of the audience or reader.

The audience must possess imaginative capacity to perceive art. However, the creation of artistic value and its perception are not identical processes. The primary difference is that art is produced during the creative process, whereas perception does not generate a new work. Perception can be described as “collaborating in creation.” Through perception, a meeting occurs between the author and reader, director and viewer, revealing the extent of art’s influence on society.

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